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**A STUDY ON UNDERSTANDING THE SIGNIFICANT ROLE OF TALENT
COACHING AND LEADERSHIP BUILDING FOR EFFECTUAL TALENT
MANAGEMENT**

Business Administration

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Abstract

Today's organization is no longer like traditional organization with hierarchical silos and bounded authority and responsibility. With the trend of "Leading by Example" expects that its workforce the intellectual capital should be innovative and creative enough along with possessing excellent inter-personal and communication skills by way of which they can perform extraordinarily better and can create competitive advantage.

Every organization aims at developing the employees by exposing them with training and development opportunities to make them more confident, skilled thus elevating their involvement, satisfaction and contribution to organization. Thus by way of this the top management in return expects that its talented employees could be converted into effective leaders through consistent investment in training, development and coaching them to understand their roles, realize their capabilities and potential and guiding them how the present and hidden potential and capabilities can be nurtured, developed and thus could be utilized to achieve organization goals and

make them more responsible, committed and loyal towards organization. By way of providing such leadership coaching more dependable, stabilized, contributing and effective talented workforce could be build up.

Keywords-*Talent coaching, Talent management, effective HRM, workforce utilization*

Introduction

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Need and scope of Talent Coaching in Talent Management

Essentials for coaching in developing Leaders-

Avoiding tendencies of becoming bad boss-It is easier to work and difficult to get work done from others similarly it is convenient to get instructions and implement and difficult to instruct others and follow up along with getting the desired results from them as per expectations along with keeping those who are working happy, satisfied, motivated and self drive. These few lines focus on why being a leader in complete form is quite arduous .An effective and successful leader is and not the one who solely has assimilated expertise in terms of requires technical or conceptual skills but is one who along with possessing these skills can correlate them with the strategic perspective of organization and can identify the talents in others, develop them and thus helps in developing new leaders within the group.

Each follower has a different set of assumptions and some particular tendencies with regard to the capabilities that his leader possess, these tendencies or capabilities if found not as per expectations dilute the relationship and effectiveness of the leader.

Thus, while organizations are investing in providing leadership coaching and preparing its leaders through coaching certain essentials needs to be transferred.

Few such tendencies are-

Self-Dilution-Both the leaders themselves as well as the followers think that the leaders or their bosses possess extra skills and expertise in comparison to them. Leaders should understand the relevance of this and should keep on adding inputs and evaluating the skill's from time to time so as their skill and performance becomes exemplified for followers or the team members to further adopt and improve their performance as well.

Heedlessness-Once the leaders or bosses possess power or authority they are been more watched more by others both by people below them as well those with equal authority .In such situations it is important that leaders should remain engaged and curious with those who report them directly , help them to achieve their results and remaining more communicative and transparent.

Avoiding Insulation-The leader once becoming successful and highly accepted wants to avoid mistakes and errors on the part of all those who work for him as well as on his part. Thus, at times when any employee will discover some problem or constraint in work will not report about the problem perceiving that the leader will not encourage this and it may lead to unexpected consequences. With feelings and environment like this employees will not share the problems and the possible hurdles thus actually will lead to more problems and severe results. This can be resolved only when the leader has created an open and collaborative environment where sharing, identifying and reporting problems and thus finding solutions for them are been highly welcomed.

Such a collaborative and open culture will nurture the talented minds to become more analytical, holistic and involved while performing work and will help them to become effective leaders under such skilful leadership.

Feeling of Collectivism-The strongest trait of being a leader is the feeling of Collectivism. Any employee who is a part of system is actually a leader. An effective and people's leader is one who is not a separate individual different from any system or any unit in an organization but is a part of such system always because leadership is not only about one who is leading but for one who is being led as a part of team or organization.

Feeling of alignment-Other important attribute essential to be incorporated in an effective leader is that they should remain aligned with the organization goals and objectives .They should be having the capability to align hierarchy of goals right from individual to team to organization which could be aligned across the hierarchical tiers.

Feeling of upliftment- The other important attribute essential to be taught to talented employees while coaching them to become effective leaders the feeling of upliftment.This would make everybody feel that their all efforts are having a purpose, direction, and outcome and that the contribution given by them is adding to organization goal accomplishment.

Defining the Leadership Bandwidth-It is important for organizations to understand that in the practice of developing leaders and nurturing them they should first be clear with the objectives and purpose of developing leadership through coaching and how would this help them in attaining the organizational goals. Every organization should be particular in building its leadership bandwidth and professionalizing their set –ups. The focus should also be largely on trends in industry with regard to the leadership development. The Focus should also be on the type of leadership demanded at global level to make leadership contribute in it fullest sense towards the growth of organization.

Preparing Leaders to be Global risk Takers-Every organization while coaching and preparing its talent workforce should keep in mind that it is not limiting itself to its organization requirement and incubating the skills which are necessary to accomplish the immediate tasks only. Rather the focus should be on developing leaders to face global challenges and expertise that can help other organization key inputs to improve organization functioning supported by key leadership qualities. For example at V-care , the management focuses on picking and developing leaders with sound inter-personal skills, initiative taking abilities, flexible in adapting to environment, willing to take risks, ethical and are ready to work globally.

Important ways to prepare Talent Reservoir for building leadership

For all this it is important that organization should in every decision right from hiring to retaining should keep a strong eye on what it wants to build in form of **leadership reservoir** and why and where it needs to show its implications both quantitatively and qualitatively.

a) Keeping employees aware with expected Leadership Behaviour -

It is important that while preparing employees to become effective leaders and prepare a strong leadership base the top management or all those whose vision and long term moves decide the future of the organization to decide and communicate to others what leadership behaviour they expect from the leaders which will help in improving the whole leadership pipeline. This leadership behaviour includes the attitude and values along with the competencies and capabilities. Attitude and values are inherent in an individual but the second part that is competencies and capabilities can be developed by training, performance development plans where performance development has a clear role.

Simply expecting that few days workshop will help employees to become leaders cannot be success until these efforts are consistent and long term. It is also important that such leaders should be counselled by highly performing leaders who can give them direction. The developing

leaders should also be able to see their career path, performance development and contribution to organization with such leadership skills.

Such efforts will help organization in building their leadership bench, identify leader at all levels, empower them, this should be accompanied by internal coaching mentoring to utilize potential leaders.

b) Developing organizational learning for effective leadership development-

While preparing employees and developing them to become effective leaders it is important that organization through its high performing leaders should focus on developing a learning environment where learning is not by force but by willingness of each employee which organization aims to transform to a leader. Learning organization as defined by Peter Senge are organization where employees are ready to expand their capacities ,nurture new ways of learning and have collective aspirations. Such organization creates an environment of leadership and togetherness.

The five main dimensions that distinguishes a learning organization which focuses on leadership development from other traditional organization are-

System thinking- It helps an organization to decide upon its priorities while taking decision with regard to different aspects of the organization. It focuses on Causes-Event-Effect-feedback and leverage.

Personal Mastery- It refers to the competency and motivation of each employee to go beyond the job related skills and continually explore new horizons. In such environment each employee should be willing for self development to realize his fullest potential. This will help in giving a sense of purpose and a greater meaning to work and develop internal locus of control and develop ability to control process and events around them.

Mental Models-This will make leaders more effective because mental modelling means in warding the perception and view about the external world as we see it. According to this model most of us view the world as per our assumptions. For learning to become independent it is important that we unearth our internal pictures to bring to surface and hold rigorously to scrutiny. This will help leaders to make their thinking open to the influence of others.

Shared Vision-Since leadership is about establishing commonality in achieving organization goals if there is no shared vision every effort will be in different diverse direction thus the motivation and encouragement to achieve result will be nullified.

Team Learning- This is important to be taught in coaching the people for becoming effective leaders because this feeling only will generate shared and collective commitment to the goals which is very important for effective leaders.

c) Identifying required competencies for developing competency framework-

The present organization demands something exceptional from leaders to bring a sea change in improving the culture, effectiveness and growth of organization. For this it is important that while coaching the leaders for occupying responsible positions and contribute effectively or the organization needs to identify key competency framework. The common competencies required for learning organization includes-

- ***Openness in leadership***-It is important that leaders should have an open attitude towards managing the diverse workforce .For this it is important that right from taking care of diversities in selection, development and promotion it is important that all information should be shared to all members.
- ***Adopting Systematic thinking***-It is important that in order to make the impact of leadership pervasive and making the organization benefitted. This requires sharing of information at different levels, breaking the traditional authority, removing the artificial

relationship between line and staff. Organization also needs to keep track on external forces that may affect leadership in organization.

- **Cultivating Creativity**-Other important trait that should be considered in developing competency framework and preparing leaders to owe organization and enhance commitment and involvement in their work is by training the workforce in becoming creative for long term, preparing leaders to accept failures and sustain their creativity in work and developing a supportive culture.
- **Developing Personal Efficacy**-This is other important competency that an effective leader needs to develop and practice, it refers to a strong belief in one's capability to influence the situation which should reflect in form of clear vision, rewarding people who contribute at best and having a learning culture where problems are taken as a part of regular working.
- **Practicing Empathy**-This helps in making the leaders more understanding to the expectations and requirement of people around them right from customers, colleagues, followers, team members, clients and others. This requires that leader should focus on developing and encouraging citizenship behaviour, encouraging employee's contribution and rewarding the performance and contribution of all.

Techniques/Strategies for Leadership Coaching

a) Conducting an informal 360 degree-Before an employee is been identified for occupying leadership role it is important to identify own strength so that the required improvements could be easily understood .For this an informal 360 degree evaluation can be of great help .In this the following can help-

a. First identifying what these strengths are and why they are relevant for organization

b. Discussion with all team members, colleagues and boss to evaluate which leadership skills should the emerging leader focus on, what could be the possible failures and flaws both for career and for relationship if these leadership skills are not properly adopted. Similarly what

would be the best of abilities that will add to success for a leader are important to be identified. The emerging or the developing leader should also focus on assessing which leadership skills of the leader the team member appreciates most so that it can further be improved to produce effective results.

c. Further the leader should try at best to show receptiveness and to create a feeling of safety targeted towards making self improvement

d. Create an open picture about yourself where the leader could openly accept that he is ready for negative feedback and absorb it professionally and appropriately accompanied with regular feedback and follow up.

b) Focusing on building strength systematically – While developing the leadership skills the following are essential to be considered-

Identify the strength to be developed-For this the focus of the leader should not only be on what he feels is important for himself but on what will be the effect of this on others because leadership is more about how others perceive. For this conducting a 360 degree evaluation can be of great help. Conducting it formally with the help of psychometric tools whereby questionnaire consisting of judging the leadership attributes present in an employee can be judged by the superior, peers and bosses quantitatively. This can consist of open ended questions concerned to the strength, flaws of an individual .In this it is important that the feedback should be genuine and employees should be honest in giving their feedback to them, to organization and to others.

Select a complementary behavior the leader would like to enhance –Other important trait or necessary competency for a effective leader to be developed is that he should be a good motivator and with his motivation ability he should enable others to travel the extra mile towards achieving success.

c) Developing effective assessment system-The scope of appraisals should be expanded and should not be limited to mere evaluating the efforts that an individual has put top accomplish the task rather as a platform to assess the areas where development is needed, identifying the potential employees adding more to the talent reservoir and further training and developing them to contribute effectively for organization.

Once this potential or the contribution of an individual is identified, new roles with respect to the career plan and exploring opportunities to identify the right successor should be aimed through assessment followed by coaching these excellent performers so as to prepare them for future roles.

d) Integrating the role of training and Development with Coaching for developing leadership- Leadership coaching demands and focuses more on making leaders independent in terms of decision making , focussing on development of others and self by providing exposure and skill updating, integrating with organization objectives and goals to direct one's efforts towards organization effectiveness. Several executive development programs aim at developing these leadership qualities in emerging talents to nourish them with required skills for e.g at **Mahindra and Mahindra** in order to nurture talent right at step one and to make young minds (Gen Y) involved in strategic issues and make them acquainted with organizational issues they follow concept of *Shadow boards* whose objective is to acquaint the young talent with top leadership issues. Here the young talented minds get the chance to share their suggestions with the Group Executive board and many of those suggestions are implemented which help them in gaining experience to understand how people at top think and skills necessary to become effective leaders.

Benefits of Leadership Coaching

Leadership coaching not only benefits the performers to become more effective and efficient thus helping them to jump high in achieving goals but also benefits the organization in

many ways. It is a mutually benefitting function that helps organization in preparing trained and competent workforce along with retaining them in longer run.

- ❖ It ensures that the strategic and interpersonal skills possessed by the leader are aligned in an effective way to the preferred leadership brand name of the organization. After coaching the leaders will feel a greater sense of common purpose and objectives aligned to the organization goals.
- ❖ Leadership coaching helps in developing a strategic vision in the employees by way of which the employees are able to tactically handle the learning from coaching in the well being of the organization
- ❖ It helps in developing a coaching culture in the organization thus setting specific techniques, process, culture and mindset of learning and making organization work more effectively. It gives a common message to all employees that the organization has concern and focuses on development and supports its workforce through coaching thus ensuring consistent growth and development .
- ❖ A trained and competent employee brings more creative ways and innovativeness in work thus enhancing the efficiency and output.
- ❖ With increase focus on coaching and continuous improvement a greater sense of job satisfaction and commitment towards the work also augments.

Conclusion

Thus it can be understood that what organization feel most important is for the sustainability of organization is its capability of developing leadership as a part of organization culture. It is only this trait and attribute that organization can think of effective talent management. In the context of talking about transformational, inspirational and motivational leadership it is important to develop the leadership skills based on the expected job/task to be delegated thus developing internally the true leaders. It is important to create an environment

where leadership can develop and nurture; organization should keep a keen focus on reward and recognition to develop leadership and focus on job content and job process coaching, role of managers in developing a leadership environment and culture matched with strategic objectives of firm.

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